

LIST OF PUBLISHED PAPERS

I. PHD THESIS:

(2008) *E-economy. Doctrinal-economic component*, Academy of Economic Studies, Bucharest

(2022) *Contribution of the mountain products to the development of Romanian agriculture*, Oradea University (forthcoming)

II. POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP:

(2014) *Smart sustainable development of e-banking, eco-banking and bio-banking based on financial and cyber security*, Romanian Academy – National Institute of Economic Studies, published as Book 1

III. VOLUME:

Author:

Book 1 (2020/2014) Covaci B., *Banking and Financial Security in E-Eco-Bio Economic Context*. Österreichisch-Rumänischer Akademischer Verein, Vienna; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4106943>

Book 2 (2020/2014) Anca Cristina Grecea, Constantin Stoican, Covaci B., *European project management – an integrated approach*. Österreichisch-Rumänischer Akademischer Verein, Vienna; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4106983>

Book 3 (2020/2012) Covaci B., *Money, Credit, Banking – from Financing to Financial System*. Österreichisch-Rumänischer Akademischer Verein, Vienna; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4106963>

Book 4 (2015) Mihai Ilie (coord.) *Piata financiara. Componenta fundamentala a pietei globale: echilibru, cooperare, integrare*, capitol Covaci B., Realizarea convergenței nominale și reale în raport cu cerințele integrării europene și cu creșterea economică în România, Editura Fundației România de Măine, București

Book 5 (2015) Alexandru T. Bogdan (coord.) et al. (Covaci B.) – 28 de autori, *Bio economic solutions for zoo-technic crisis, through sustainable agri-food independence and sovereignty of the Euro Atlantic Romania*. Romanian Academy Publishing House

Book 6 (2012) Alexandru T. Bogdan (coord.) et. al. (Covaci B.) – 18 de autori, *Biodiversity of the farm animals and eco-bioeconomics significances in the food security context – Volumul I*, Romanian Academy Publishing House

Book 7 (2012) Alexandru T. Bogdan (coord.) et. al. (Covaci B.) – 28 de autori, *Biodiversity of the farm animals and eco-bioeconomics significances in the food security context – Volumul II*, Romanian Academy Publishing House

Editor/author (volumes):

V1 (2011) Bojkovic Z., Kacprzyk J., Mastorakis N., Mladenov V., Zadeh L., Zemliak A., Covaci B., Bogdan A., Lazaroiu G., *Recent Researches in Energy & Environment*, Cambridge University, Cambridge, UK, 2011; Indexed in BDI WSEAS: www.wseas.org, Repec: <http://ideas.repec.org/s/ris/sphedp.html> și ACM: www.acm.org

V2 (2010) Lagakos S., Perlovsky L., Jha M., Covaci B., Zaharim A., Mastorakis N., *Recent Advances in Computer Engineering and Applications*, Harvard University, Cambridge MA, SUA, 2010; Indexed in BDI WSEAS: www.wseas.org, Repec: <http://ideas.repec.org/s/ris/sphedp.html>, ACM: www.acm.org și ISI Proceeding Thomson (Clarivate)

V3 (2010) Lagakos S., Perlovsky L., Jha M., Covaci B., Zaharim A., Mastorakis N., *Proceedings of the 4th Wseas International Conference on Circuits, Systems, Signal and Telecommunications*, Harvard University, Cambridge MA, SUA, 2010; Indexed in BDI WSEAS: www.wseas.org, Repec: <http://ideas.repec.org/s/ris/sphedp.html>, ACM: www.acm.org și ISI Proceeding Thomson (Clarivate)

V4 (2010) Frunzeti T., Hanganu M., et al. Covaci B., *Proceedings of the The 34th Annual Congress American Romanian Academy of Arts and Sciences (ARA) – Carol I National Defence University Romania*, Ecole Polytechnique de Montreal, Canada, 2010

Coordinator:

V6 (2013) Bogdan A.T., Ipate I., Covaci B., Innovation activities in juridical science for sustaining environment, safety and food security, biotechnology and eco-economy through doctoral research, Economica Publishing House, Romania Academy, Bucuresti

V7 (2013) Bogdan A.T., Ipate I., Covaci B., Innovation activities in dental medicine doctoral research in order to sustain bioeconomy and biodiversity desiderata, Economica Publishing House, Romania Academy, Bucuresti

V8 (2013) Bogdan A.T., Ipate I., Covaci B., Solutii inter-multi-disciplinare in contextul strategiilor ecoeconomice si bioeconomice pentru siguranta si securitatea alimentelor si furajelor din ecosisteme antropice, Economica Publishing House, Romania Academy, Bucuresti

V9 (2013) Bogdan A.T., Ipate I., Covaci B., Innovation activities in biodiversity and eco-bio-economics doctoral research for safety and food security, Economica Publishing House, Romania Academy, Bucuresti

III. ARTICOLE INDEXATE BDI:

First author or co-author:

IS11 (2021) Covaci, B. 2021. "Apparel Industry in the EU–China Exports and Circular Economy", *Autex Research Journal*. Published Online: 02 Apr 2021. Impact factor 2020 – 1,375. <https://doi.org/10.2478/aut-2021-0010>

IS12 (2010) Nicolae, D., Andreica, M., Jaradat, M., Covaci, B., Birzu, M. The progress offered by the subtle sets theory (SST) in the investigation of the socio-economic processes, *Recent Advances in Business Administration* (Proceedings of the 9th WSEAS Int. Conf. on Artificial Intelligence, Knowledge Engineering and Data Bases - AIKED '10), University of Cambridge, UK; ISI Thomson (Clarivate)

BDI1 Covaci B., Avădănei V., Covaci M., Avădănei L., onorific Rey R. 2021. Îndrumar privind antreprenoriatul montan, CE-MONT, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5578264>

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- BDI4** Covaci B., 2021a. Mountain social development models, between principality, conscience and evolution. An overview, *Journal for Freedom of Conscience*
- BDI5** Covaci B., 2021b. Modelele de dezvoltare socială din zona montană a Terrei, între principialitate și evoluție. *Ziarul munților*, nr. 5, CE-MONT
- BDI6** Covaci B., 2021c. Romanian mountain entrepreneurship of the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors, *Psycho-Social View Journal*, September 2/2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5568862>
- BDI7** Covaci B., 2021d. World contexts of entrepreneurship, as support for specific economic contexts of mountain investments, *Psycho-Social View Journal*, September 2/2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5568862>
- BDI8** Covaci B., 2021e. Romanian mountain entrepreneurship for industry, construction and services, *Psycho-Social View Journal*, September 2/2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5568862>
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- BDI11** Covaci B., 2021h. Forecast regarding mountain entrepreneurship of the food and services. Evidence from agritourism, *Mountain Perspective Journal*, September 2/2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5568821>
- BDI12** Covaci B., 2021i. Food and services sectors in Central And Eastern European Countries. Case study of mountain area, *Mountain Perspective Journal*, September 2/2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5568821>
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- BDI14** Covaci B., 2021k. The Romanian mountain product, probiotic in the context of COVID-19. Case study on mountain producers in Romania. Conferința anuală CE-MONT - Journal of Montanology 2021
- BDI15** Covaci B., 2021l. Brîndușa S. Covaci The sustainability of the mountain area from the North-East region of Romania through Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles sectors, *Mountain Perspective Journal* 2/January 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486657>
- BDI16** Covaci B., 2021m. Brîndușa S. Covaci Statistics regarding online courses and the new pandemic conditions, *Mountain Perspective Journal* 2/January 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486607>
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- BDI19** (2020) Covaci B. Construction Industry: Entrepreneurship, Circular Economy and Environment Protection. Case Study of Romanian Mountains Area, *Annals of Oradea University – Fascicle: Environment Protection. Revistă indexată în CABI, SSRN, DRJI, ARI* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4192181>
- BDI20** (2020) Covaci B., Brejea R., Economic development of the European mountain area between 2014-2018: a statistical approach, *Annals of the Academy of Romanian Scientists Series on Agriculture, Silviculture and Veterinary Medicine Sciences*: 9 (2). Indexat în Zenodo, SSRN <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4192341>
- BDI21** (2020) Covaci B. Natural Honey Market: Eu28 And Brics Competitiveness. Evidences Regarding Mountain Natural Honey, *Journal of EcoAgroTourism, Romanian Society for Information Technology In Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism (ROSITA)*, 16(2) (2020). Indexat in EBSCO, Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4192039>
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- BDI23** (2019) Covaci B. Antreprenoriatul, suport al dezvoltării umane. studiu de caz privind activitățile administrative și de suport și activitățile profesionale, științifice și tehnice din Regiunea de Nord-Est a României. *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință* 7.2 (2019): 46-57. Indexat ERIH, CEEOL, SSRN, ARI, Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4193985>
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- BDI25** (2017) Covaci B. Correlation Between Public Funding and Non-Ferrous Industry. Evidence from CEE and Romania. *Network Intelligence Studies*, issue 8; indexat in REPEC, DOAJ, Ulrichs, CEEOL, EBSCO, EconLit, EconBIZ, IndexCopernicus, Georgetown University Library, Scientific Indexing Services, EuroInternet, Scientific Central, New Jour <https://doaj.org/article/9210782acc5e4fcb96f92af79835e513> <https://ideas.repec.org/a/cmj/network/y2016i8p117-123.html> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4194676>
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BDI32 (2015) Covaci B. The influence of the globalization on causality between energetic sector and differentiated wages, Impact of Socio-economic and Technological Transformations at National, European and International Level (ISETT), Institute for World Economy, Romanian Academy, vol. 1; indexat in REPEC, SSRN, NOS

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